

Chemical Investigations on Seeds of *Sarcostigma kleinii*

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Sarcostigma kleinii W and A (Icacinaeae) is a large shrub-by climber growing abundantly in the eastern and western regions of the peninsula neighbouring Cochin, Travancore and Konkan. The plant, also known as *puvanna*, *puvenii*, *odal* or *adal* bears fleshy fruits of bright orange-red or orange-yellow colour. The seed fat is reported¹ highly efficacious in rheumatic disorders and also used as an illuminant.

The seeds (2 kg) of the plant procured from Kottayam, Kerala (Voucher specimen preserved) were decorticated. The kernels were pounded and repeatedly percolated with ethanol at ambient temperature. The ethanolic extract was distilled under reduced pressure to yield a dark brown thick concentrate which was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), diethyl ether and ethyl acetate. The diethyl ether and ethyl acetate extractives being identical on tlc were mixed and chromatographed over silica gel column. Elution with varying proportions of petroleum ether, benzene and methanol gave four compounds (1-4).

Compound 1 on crystallisation with diethyl ether-ethanol mixture furnished colourless shining flakes (487 mg) of waxy nature, m.p. 70–71°. From all accounts it appeared to be a common fatty acid. In its ir spectrum the band at 1 412 cm⁻¹ indicated CH₂ adjacent to carboxylic group and the 730 and 722 bands were for methylene chain rocking. However, the bands at 2 920, 2 850, 1 700, 1 432, 1 298 and 940 cm⁻¹ and the evenly spaced bands at 1 316, 1 298, 1 280, 1 260, 1 240, 1 222, 1 202 and 1 186 cm⁻¹ were in close proximity to the ir spectrum reported² for dimer of stearic acid. The ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) of the compound accounted for a total of 72 (36 × 2) protons. There were 6 protons for 2 (1 × 2) methyl groups at δ 0.88 (t) and 64 protons for 32 (16 × 2) methylene groups, resolved in three distinct peaks at δ 1.26 (s), 1.64 (m) and 2.36 (t) respectively for 28 (14 × 2) CH₂, 2 (1 × 2) CH₂ adjacent to methyl groups and 2 (1 × 2) CH₂ neighbouring carboxylic groups. The 2 hydroxyl protons could not be resolved. The ¹³C nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) exhibited 12 signals for 12 carbon atoms as against 18 carbon atoms indicating the 7 carbon atoms to be in similar environment³. Since it is a dimer, the ¹³C chemical shift values of only one unit will be exhibited (Table 1) It showed a quasimolecular ion peak at *m/z* 567 [M(C₃₆H₇₂O₄)-H]⁻ in the negative FAB-MS spectrum and also analysed for (C₁₈H₃₆O₂)₂, supporting its dimeric nature. Compound 1 on

saponification gave a waxy product, m.p. 68–70°, M⁺ 284, identified as stearic acid by glc of the methyl derivative. On the basis of the data discussed above its structure was derived as chelated dimer of stearic acid. The extensive literature survey reveals that this compound has not been isolated from any plant so far. Therefore, this could be a novel compound designated as Sarcostigmer being reported for the first time from this source vis-a-vis from nature.

Sarcostigmer

Compound 2 on column chromatography and crystallisations furnished orange leaflets (333 mg), m.p. 210°, exhibiting characteristic colour reactions of anthraquinones⁴. The compound analysed for C₁₆H₁₂O₅; λ_{max} (EtOH) 223 (OH), 252 (benzenoid), 264, 286 and 427 nm (quinonoid); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 460, 1 035 (OH), 1 685 (free C=O), 1 640 (chelated C=O) and 1 570, 750 cm⁻¹ (aromatic); *m/z* 284 (M⁺); δ (CDCl₃; 90 MHz) 7.0 (H-2), 7.55 (H-4), 7.28 (H-5), 6.6 (H-7), 3.85 (OCH₃) and 2.38 (CH₃). Comparison of the data with that of the literature established the identity of the compound 2 as physcion, confirmed by its acetate, m.p. 182° (M⁺ 368) and co-tlc with an authentic sample⁵.

TABLE 1-¹³C NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUND 1

Carbon no	δ (ppm)	Assignments
		(O)
		C-OH
C-1	179.9	CH ₂
C-2	33.9	CH ₂
C-3	24.7	CH ₂
C-4 to C-10	29.7	(CH ₂) ₇
C-11	29.42	CH ₂
C-12	29.34	CH ₂
C-13	29.22	CH ₂
C-14	29.1	CH ₂
C-15	29.5	CH ₂
C-16	31.9	CH ₂
C-17	22.7	CH ₂
C-18	14.1	CH ₃

NOTE

Anthraquinone positive compounds **3** and **4** were purified through tlc and crystallisations as dark-red and red powder respectively, m.ps. >300°, but could not be characterised due to poor yield.

The kernel meal on percolation with petroleum ether yielded a light orange coloured fat⁶ (52%) having a.v. 4.0, s.v. 186.7, i.v. 75.0 and η_{sp}^{30} 1.4650. The fat was processed for fatty acid methyl esters which on glc (DEGS column on chromosorb 85–100 mesh; column temp. 185°; 50 ml/min N₂ carrier) revealed the presence of myristic 0.59, palmitic 6.64, stearic 41.41, arachidic 1.85, oleic 28.32 and linoleic 21.19% acids. The unsaponifiable matter (1.44%) gave β -sitosterol, m.p. 140°, identified by ir, ms and acetate.

The results prove that the plant has potentiality to serve as a source of semi-drying fat. The colouring matter obtained in good yield could be utilised as a source of natural dye. The compound sarcostigmer is of interest to polymer chemists. The processed seed meal having 42% protein and

balanced amino acid composition⁷ may go as a feed additive for cattle and fish.

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